

1 Astrometric precision for direct fringe detection (v1)

1.1 Introduction

The astrometric precision of a scanning satellite using direct fringe detection is evaluated using a simplified analytical model. The model takes into account diffraction by the interferometer aperture, fringe smearing due to finite bandwidth, finite pixel width and fringe motion during the sample interval. Photon noise for the fringes with a uniform background is taken into account, and also detector readout noise. Numerical results are given for a limited range of model parameters.

1.2 Notations

General variables:

(x, y)	linear coordinates in the pupil plane [m]
(ξ, η)	angular coordinates in the focal plane [rad]
t	time [s]
λ	wavelength [m]

Input parameters:

ω	scan speed [rad s^{-1}]
τ	total integration time on object [s]
G	geometrical factor for parallax determination (~ 2)
N_i	number of interferometers
B	interferometer baseline [m]
D	diameter (or width) of each pupil [m]
F	focal length [m]
λ_0	central wavelength of the wavelength band [m]
$\Delta\lambda$	wavelength bandwidth [m]
T_λ	intensity transmittance ($T_0 = \text{effective value in } \Delta\lambda$)
Q_λ	detector quantum efficiency ($Q_0 = \text{effective value in } \Delta\lambda$)
$\Delta\xi$	angular pixel size in scan direction [rad]
$\Delta\eta$	angular pixel size in transverse direction [rad]
N_ξ	number of pixels per chip in scan direction
r	detector rms readout noise [e^-]
f_λ	monochromatic stellar photon flux [$\text{ph m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$]
b_λ	monochromatic background photon flux [$\text{ph m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1} \text{rad}^{-2}$]

Calculated quantities:

I_λ	two-dimensional monochromatic image [$\text{ph s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1} \text{rad}^{-2}$]
J_λ	one-dimensional monochromatic image [$\text{ph s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1} \text{rad}^{-1}$]
K_λ	integrated/sampled monochromatic image [$\text{ph}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$]
c_j	single-pixel detected image [e^-]
C_j	detected image after time-delayed integration [e^-]
S_j	detected image including background noise [e^-]
σ_ξ	angular precision in scan direction from one chip crossing [rad]
σ_a	astrometric precision in parallax [rad]

1.3 Some basic assumptions

According to Allen (1973) the stellar flux can be approximately expressed in terms of the *BVRI* magnitudes as:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} f_{440 \text{ nm}} &= 1.55 \times 10^{17-0.4B} \\ f_{550 \text{ nm}} &= 1.11 \times 10^{17-0.4V} \\ f_{700 \text{ nm}} &= 0.65 \times 10^{17-0.4R} \\ f_{900 \text{ nm}} &= 0.40 \times 10^{17-0.4I} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

the unit being $[\text{ph m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}]$ in all cases. It is normally more convenient to express the flux in terms of the magnitude in a fixed passband (such as *V*) and a colour index (such as *V-I*). Assuming that the logarithm of the flux can be linearly interpolated in wavelength we have from (1)

$$\log_{10} f_{\lambda}[V, (V-I)] \simeq 17.05 - 0.4V + \frac{\lambda - 550 \text{ nm}}{350 \text{ nm}} [0.4(V-I) - 0.45] \quad (2)$$

It can be noted that the spectrum is essentially flat from *B* to *I* for stars of $V-I \sim 1.1$, corresponding to unreddened spectral type G5.

If the sky background corresponds to one star of magnitude V_b per square arcsec, and has the colour index $(V-I)_b$, then:

$$b_{\lambda} = 4.25 \times 10^{10} f_{\lambda}[V_b, (V-I)_b] \quad (3)$$

The total integrated flux in a passband defined by $T_{\lambda}Q_{\lambda}$ may be written as

$$\int_{\lambda_{\min}}^{\lambda_{\max}} Q_{\lambda} T_{\lambda} f_{\lambda} d\lambda = Q_0 T_0 f_0 \Delta\lambda \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta\lambda$ is (for instance) the FWHM passband width and Q_0, T_0, f_0 are effective quantities in that passband. This type of substitution is sometimes useful to reduce the complexity of the formulae.

It is assumed that the (stellar and background) flux is integrated during the star's passage across the N_{ξ} pixels of a single chip, and then read out (adding readout noise to each pixel value). Fringe dispersion can be treated as two or more separate channels, each with a bandwidth set by the transverse pixel size and cross dispersion.

1.4 Formation of fringes

Linear coordinates (x, y) , expressed in [m], are used in the pupil plane, with x in the scan direction; angular coordinates (ξ, η) , expressed in [rad], are used in the detector plane. In the monochromatic case, and in absence of aberrations, the basic relation between the stellar flux density f_{λ} (per unit area) in the pupil plane and the stellar intensity I_{λ} (per steradian) in the image plane is given by the Fraunhofer diffraction formula:

$$I_{\lambda}(\xi, \eta) = \frac{f_{\lambda}}{\lambda^2} \left| \iint a_{\lambda}(x, y) \exp \left[i \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (x\xi + y\eta) \right] dx dy \right|^2 \quad (5)$$

where $a_\lambda(x, y)$ is the (in general complex) amplitude transmittance of the instrument. With $\iint |a_\lambda(x, y)|^2 dx dy = AT_\lambda$, where A is the total pupil area, Parseval's relation gives $\iint I_\lambda(\xi, \eta) d\xi d\eta = AT_\lambda f_\lambda$, as required by the conservation of energy. In the following the wavefront errors are neglected (although the fringe visibility may be introduced at a later stage) and the transmittance is assumed to be uniform over the pupil; thus $a_\lambda(x, y) = \sqrt{T_\lambda} P(x, y)$ where $P(x, y)$ is the pupil function (= 1 inside the pupil, 0 outside the pupil). Then:

$$\begin{aligned} I_\lambda(\xi, \eta) &= \frac{T_\lambda f_\lambda}{\lambda^2} \left| \iint P(x, y) \exp \left[i \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (x\xi + y\eta) \right] dx dy \right|^2 \\ &= \frac{T_\lambda f_\lambda}{\lambda^2} \iiint P(x, y) P(x-u, y-v) \exp \left[i \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (u\xi + v\eta) \right] dx dy du dv \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Defining the two-dimensional MTF as the autocorrelation function of the pupil function,

$$M(u, v) = \frac{1}{A} \iint P(x, y) P(x-u, y-v) dx dy \quad (7)$$

we have:

$$I_\lambda(\xi, \eta) = \frac{AT_\lambda f_\lambda}{\lambda^2} \iint M(u, v) \exp \left[i \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (u\xi + v\eta) \right] du dv \quad (8)$$

If the transverse pixel size is large enough to collect all the light diffracted along η (for a single wavelength), we need to consider only the one-dimensional monochromatic intensity, expressed in [ph s⁻¹ m⁻¹ rad⁻¹]:

$$\begin{aligned} J_\lambda(\xi) &\equiv \int I_\lambda(\xi, \eta) d\eta \\ &= \frac{AT_\lambda f_\lambda}{\lambda} \int M(u, 0) \exp \left(i \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} u\xi \right) du \\ &= \frac{2AT_\lambda f_\lambda}{\lambda} \int_0^{B+D} M(u) \cos \left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} u\xi \right) du \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where we write $M(u)$ for $M(u, 0)$ and make use of the symmetry of the MTF, and the fact that $M(u) = 0$ for $|u| > B + D$, the maximum extension of the pupil in the x direction.

1.5 Detection of fringes

The fringe pattern $J_\lambda(\xi)$ is defined with the central fringe at $\xi = 0$. Actually the fringes move with angular velocity ω across the detector, and the instantaneous intensity at the fixed point ξ on the detector should be written $J_\lambda(\xi - \omega t)$, where time t is reckoned from the passage of the central fringe across the line $\xi = 0$. During the detection process the incoming photon flux is integrated over the pixel width [say, $(n-1)\Delta\xi < \xi < n\Delta\xi$, where n is the pixel number], time [say, $(k-1)\Delta t < t < k\Delta t$, where k is the time sample number], and wavelength (taking into account the quantum efficiency Q_λ). The expected number of electrons produced by the star light in pixel n during sample k is, therefore,

$$c(n, k) = \int_0^\infty Q_\lambda \int_{(k-1)\Delta t}^{k\Delta t} \int_{(n-1)\Delta\xi}^{n\Delta\xi} J_\lambda(\xi - \omega t) d\xi dt d\lambda \quad (10)$$

If the distance travelled in one sample time accurately matches the pixel width, $\omega\Delta t = \Delta\xi$, then evidently $c(n, k)$ depends only on $j = n - k$ and we find

$$c_j = \Delta t \int_0^\infty Q_\lambda \int_{-\Delta\xi}^{\Delta\xi} \left(1 - \frac{|s|}{\Delta\xi}\right) J_\lambda(j\Delta\xi + s) ds d\lambda \quad (11)$$

Through time-delayed integration this charge is accumulated as the image moves across the chip; after N_ξ samples the total charge becomes

$$C_j = N_\xi \Delta t \int_0^\infty Q_\lambda K_\lambda(j\Delta\xi) d\lambda \quad (12)$$

where

$$K_\lambda(\xi) = \int_{-\Delta\xi}^{\Delta\xi} \left(1 - \frac{|s|}{\Delta\xi}\right) J_\lambda(\xi + s) ds \quad (13)$$

Insertion of (7) gives

$$K_\lambda(\xi) = \frac{2AT_\lambda f_\lambda \Delta\xi}{\lambda} \int_0^{B+D} M(u) \left[\frac{\sin(\pi u \Delta\xi / \lambda)}{\pi u \Delta\xi / \lambda} \right]^2 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} u \xi\right) du \quad (14)$$

Although the 'charge image' C_j is a discrete series, it can be regarded as a sampling of the continuous function $C(\xi)$, with $C_j = C(j\Delta\xi)$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} C(\xi) &= N_\xi \Delta t \int_0^\infty Q_\lambda K_\lambda(\xi) d\lambda \\ &= 2AN_\xi \Delta t \Delta\xi \int_0^{B+D} \int_0^\infty \frac{Q_\lambda T_\lambda f_\lambda}{\lambda} M(u) \operatorname{sinc}^2\left(\frac{\pi}{\lambda} u \Delta\xi\right) \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} u \xi\right) d\lambda du \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Changing to the new variable $w = u\lambda_0/\lambda$ this can be written

$$C(\xi) = 2AN_\xi \Delta t \Delta\xi Q_0 T_0 f_0 \frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda_0} \int_0^{w_{\max}} \bar{M}(w) \operatorname{sinc}^2\left(\frac{\pi}{\lambda_0} w \Delta\xi\right) \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda_0} w \xi\right) dw \quad (16)$$

where Q_0, T_0, f_0 and $\Delta\lambda$ are defined as in (4), $w_{\max} = (B + D)\lambda_0/\lambda_{\min}$, and

$$\bar{M}(w) = \frac{1}{Q_0 T_0 f_0 \Delta\lambda} \int_{\lambda_{\min}}^{\lambda_{\max}} Q_\lambda T_\lambda f_\lambda M(w\lambda/\lambda_0) d\lambda \quad (17)$$

is the flux-weighted mean modulation transfer function.

Equation (16) gives $C(\xi)$ in terms of the cosine transform of the effective transfer function, $U(w) = \bar{M}(w) \operatorname{sinc}^2(\pi w \Delta\xi / \lambda_0)$. The factor $N = AN_\xi \Delta t Q_0 T_0 f_0 \Delta\lambda$ is the total number of stellar photons detected during the crossing of the chip, so an alternative form of (16) is simply

$$C(\xi) = \frac{2N\Delta\xi}{\lambda_0} \int_0^{w_{\max}} U(w) \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda_0} w \xi\right) dw \quad (18)$$

The total number of photons is also obtained by adding up the numbers C_j . Since $C(\xi)$ resulted from a convolution by (among other things) a rectangular function of width $\Delta\xi$ it follows that

$$\sum_{-\infty}^{+\infty} C_j = \frac{1}{\Delta\xi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} C(\xi) d\xi \quad (19)$$

holds strictly. Inserting (16) and performing the integration shows that the sum is, indeed, equal to N .

1.6 Precision of image location

The expected number of detected photons in slot j is $C_j + AT_0Q_0b_0\Delta\lambda N_\xi\Delta t\Delta\xi\Delta\eta$, where b_0 is the background flux at the mean wavelength defined in analogy with f_0 in (4). The photon noise is the square root of this number. To this must be added the readout noise, having an rms value of r counts. The signal n_j can thus be regarded as resulting from a Poisson process with expectation $S(\xi_j) = C(\xi_j - \xi_0) + \beta$, where

$$\beta = AT_0Q_0b_0\Delta\lambda N_\xi\Delta t\Delta\xi\Delta\eta + r^2 \quad (20)$$

is the effective background level. The maximum likelihood estimator can be used to estimate ξ_0 , β and a scaling factor for the stellar intensity (such as f_0) by minimizing

$$L(\xi_0, \beta, f_0) = \sum_j [S(\xi_j) - n_j \ln S(\xi_j)] \quad (21)$$

Monte Carlo experiments are needed to study how accurate the resulting estimates actually are. However, provided the total number of counts is not too small, the Cramér–Rao bound should provide a realistic estimate of the precision of ξ_0 . If the fringes are not too badly sampled, the CR bound can be approximated by

$$\sigma_\xi = \left[\frac{1}{\Delta\xi} \int \frac{[S'(\xi)]^2}{S(\xi)} d\xi \right]^{-1/2} \quad (22)$$

Unfortunately it does not seem possible to evaluate this integral analytically in terms of the effective transfer function $U(w)$. It is however possible in the special case when background, bandwidth and sampling effects are negligible, i.e. for $S(\xi) = C(\xi)$ with $U(w) = M(w)$. Assuming furthermore a symmetrical pupil, we find in this case that the integral in (22) is proportional to $\iint P(x, y)x^2 dx dy = Ax_{\text{rms}}^2$, leading to the following expression for the limiting astrometric accuracy:

$$\sigma_\xi \geq \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{\lambda}{2x_{\text{rms}}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \quad (23)$$

On the other hand, in the limit when the background noise is dominating, the variation of the denominator in the integrand can be neglected. This suggests that we write

$$\int \frac{[S'(\xi)]^2}{S(\xi)} d\xi = \frac{1}{\beta + \bar{C}} \int [S'(\xi)]^2 d\xi \quad (24)$$

where $\bar{C}$ is a suitable average of $C(\xi)$. Now, the latter integral can be analytically evaluated in terms of $U(w)$:

$$\int [C'(\xi)]^2 d\xi = \frac{4\pi^2 N^2 \Delta\xi^2}{\lambda_0^3} 2 \int_0^{w_{\text{max}}} U(w)^2 w^2 dw \quad (25)$$

A reasonable guess for $\bar{C}$ is some fraction of the maximum $C(\xi)$, say $\bar{C} = kC(0)$, with k probably being of the order of 0.5 (the value is further discussed below). Then

$$\bar{C} = \frac{kN\Delta\xi}{\lambda_0} 2 \int_0^{w_{\text{max}}} U(w) dw \quad (26)$$

It is clear that the final expression for σ_ξ will depend on certain moments of $U(w)$. From the moments we may define two characteristic numbers, both of dimension length:

$$u_0 = 2 \int_0^{w_{\max}} U(w) dw, \quad u_2 = \left[\frac{2}{u_0} \int_0^{w_{\max}} U(w)^2 w^2 dw \right]^{1/2} \quad (27)$$

from which

$$\sigma_\xi = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{\lambda_0}{u_2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \left[k + \frac{\beta \lambda_0}{N \Delta \xi u_0} \right]^{1/2} \quad (28)$$

The quantity u_0 is mainly determined by the size of the pupils: in the limiting case $U(w) = M(w)$ with rectangular pupils we have simply $u_0 = 2D$. Thus λ_0/u_0 is approximately the angular size of the diffraction envelope of each pupil, and $\beta \lambda_0/(N \Delta \xi u_0)$ can be interpreted as the ratio of background counts within the diffraction envelope to the number of stellar counts. The quantity u_2 , on the other hand, is mainly determined by the length of the baseline. Again in the limiting case $U(w) = M(w)$ and a small D/B ratio we find $u_2 = B/\sqrt{6}$. Comparison of (28) with the theoretical formula (23) for the case when $2x_{\text{rms}} = B$ thus suggests that $k = 1/6$. A similar comparison for a filled rectangular aperture gives $k = 1/5$, while a filled circular aperture gives $k = 0.187\dots$. Numerical calculations including some background noise indicate however that $k = 0.5$ may be a more realistic figure, which shall therefore be used in the following.

1.7 Astrometric precision

The astrometric precision is finally estimated as

$$\sigma_a = G \left(\frac{\tau_1}{N_i \tau} \right)^{1/2} \sigma_\xi \quad (29)$$

where $\tau_1 = N_\xi \Delta t = N_\xi \Delta \xi / \omega$ is the time required for the image to move across one chip, N_i is the number of interferometers (each with a total integration time τ on the star), and $G \sim 2$ the factor relating the scanning geometry to the determination of parallaxes.

1.8 Summary of formulae

The complete set of formulae needed to estimate the astrometric precision is summarised hereafter. B and D are implicitly given by the pupil function $P(x, y)$.

$$M(u) = \frac{1}{A} \iint P(x, y)P(x - u, y) dx dy \quad (30)$$

$$U(w) = \left(\frac{\sin(\pi w \Delta \xi / \lambda_0)}{\pi w \Delta \xi / \lambda_0} \right)^2 \frac{\int Q_\lambda T_\lambda f_\lambda M(w \lambda / \lambda_0) d\lambda}{\int Q_\lambda T_\lambda f_\lambda d\lambda} \quad (31)$$

$$w_{\max} = (B + D)\lambda_0 / \lambda_{\min} \quad (32)$$

$$u_0 = 2 \int_0^{w_{\max}} U(w) dw \quad (33)$$

$$u_2 = \left[\frac{2}{u_0} \int_0^{w_{\max}} U(w)^2 w^2 dw \right]^{1/2} \quad (34)$$

$$N = AN_\xi \Delta t \int Q_\lambda T_\lambda f_\lambda d\lambda \quad (35)$$

$$\beta = AN_\xi \Delta t \Delta \xi \Delta \eta \int Q_\lambda T_\lambda b_\lambda d\lambda + r^2 \quad (36)$$

$$\sigma_\xi = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{\lambda_0}{u_2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \left[k + \frac{\beta \lambda_0}{N \Delta \xi u_0} \right]^{1/2} \quad (k \sim 0.5) \quad (37)$$

$$\sigma_a = G \left(\frac{N_\xi \Delta t}{N_i \tau} \right)^{1/2} \sigma_\xi \quad (G \sim 2) \quad (38)$$

1.9 A reference example

Even in the present simplified analysis the astrometric precision depends on a large number of parameters, and only a very small subset of the parameter space can realistically be explored. Here, a specific point in parameter space is selected as reference, and variations along selected lines through the reference point are explored in order to illustrate how the precision depends on some critical parameters. The reference values for the parameters are summarised in Table 1. The resulting σ_a as function of the V magnitude is shown in Table 2. Figure 1 shows the function $C(\xi)$, i.e. the expected number of charges as function of position.

The variation with some of the parameters is shown in Figures 2 to 6. The last two figures, illustrating the dependence on wavelength passband, are relevant for fringe dispersion: the standard error from a single spectrometric channel of width $\Delta \lambda$ is divided by the square root of the number of channels, taken to be $(400 \text{ nm} / \Delta \lambda)$, in order to give a number representative of the total precision.

Table 1. Reference parameters for analysis of precision

Parameter	Reference	Alternative values	Figure
ω	120 arcsec s ⁻¹		
τ	1500 s		
G	2.0		
N_i	2		
B	2.4 m	1–4 m	3
D	0.6 m (circular)	0.4–1.0 m	4
F	60 m		
$F\Delta\xi$	5 μm	1–10 μm	2, 3
$F\Delta\eta$	40 μm		
r	5	0, 10	2, 5, 6
N_ξ	8192		
$T_\lambda Q_\lambda$	0.5		
λ_0	650 nm		
$\Delta\lambda$	400 nm	10–500 nm	4, 5, 6
k	0.5		
V	15.0	10–20	6 and Table 2
$V-I$	1.0		
V_b	20.0		
$(V-I)_b$	1.0		

Table 2. Astrometric precision as function of magnitude. All other parameters are set to their reference values in Table 1.

V	σ_a	V	σ_a	V	σ_a
mag	μas	mag	μas	mag	μas
10.0	1.0	14.0	6.2	18.0	47.1
11.0	1.5	15.0	9.9	19.0	91.1
12.0	2.4	16.0	16.0	20.0	195.1
13.0	3.9	17.0	26.7	21.0	451.9

Figure 1. The curve is the continuous function $C(\xi)$ for the reference example. The points on the curve are shown at intervals of 0.1 pixel.

Figure 2. Astrometric precision versus pixel width for different values of the readout noise. In this and subsequent figures, all other parameters are set to the reference values in Table 1.

Figure 3. Astrometric precision versus baseline length for different pixel widths.

Figure 4. Astrometric precision versus wavelength passband for different aperture diameters.

Figure 5. Astrometric precision (times $\sqrt{\Delta\lambda/400 \text{ nm}}$) versus passband width for different values of the readout noise.

Figure 6. Same as Figure 5 but for magnitude $V = 20$.